

THE EFFECT OF COATING BACTERIA-INOCULATED SEED WITH CHITOSAN AND SODIUM ALGINATE BIOPOLYMERS ON SOME GROWTH PARAMETERS OF BEAN PLANT

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ABSTRACT. In recent years, microbial fertilizers have been suggested as alternatives to reduce the negative impacts of agricultural activities. However, the application of microbial fertilizers in agriculture is restricted due to their sensitivity. The purpose of this study is to avoid or eliminate these limitations by inoculating bean plant seeds with rhizobium bacteria and then coating them with chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers to protect the viability of the bacteria for three months. The coating of the bacteria provides a safe environment for their growth, increases their sustainability, and can provide protection. To achieve this objective, seeds of the Yunus 90 bean cultivar were inoculated with rhizobium bacteria in a liquid formulation (1×10^8 CFU) after surface sterilization. After inoculation, chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers at a concentration of 1% were used to coat the bacteria. After inoculation, the seeds coated with biopolymers were dried in a dark place for 1-2 hours, then packed and stored for 90 days. After 3 months, a controlled greenhouse experiment was conducted in which the seeds were planted in pots containing sterile sand and perlite. At the same time, biopolymer-coated bean seeds inoculated with bacteria are grown as a control. As a result, different effects of coatings with the biopolymers chitosan and sodium alginate on bacteria-inoculated seeds of a bean plant were shown, and these differences were found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). It was found that the coating with the biopolymer sodium alginate was more effective than chitosan in maintaining bacterial survival and increasing some yield components compared to the treated control sample. Bean seeds, after being inoculated with rhizobium bacteria and coated with biopolymers, the bacteria may maintain their shelf life by around 50% when considering the sensitivity of traditional microbial fertilizers applications.

Keywords: *Chitosan, coating, inoculation, rhizobium, sodium alginate*

INTRODUCTION

One of the biggest problems in food production is the excessive use of toxic agrochemicals, which have significant negative impacts on the environment, food safety, and consequently human health during crop production. Due to the negative effects of excessive and incorrect use of chemical fertilizers, the development of microbial inoculants has increased worldwide [1; 2]. One of the ways to avoid the excessive use of chemicals is the controlled and targeted distribution of microorganisms and chemical agents. Appropriate, controlled, and targeted distribution can be achieved through the encapsulation method, and this has proven to be a viable way to provide nutrients for organic and sustainable crop production.

The main benefits of the encapsulation of biological and chemical agents include continuous and controlled release, higher efficiency, and a relatively positive impact on the environment [3]. According to recent studies, several experimental polymer-based formulations have been developed [4], and these formulations can act as bacterial carriers [5]. When the polymers used for coating were decomposed by soil microorganisms, the bacteria were slowly released into the soil and the microorganisms were protected from biotic and abiotic stress [4]. Shcherbakova et al. [6] found in a study that coating of chickpea and soybean seeds in alginate microspheres after inoculation with *Mezorhizobium ciceri* ST-282 and

Bradyrhizobium japonicum M8 significantly increased both the number and weight of nodules. Application of chitosan to seeds promotes seed germination, growth, and yield [7; 8], disease control or activation of innate immunity of plants against pathogens and mitigation of various abiotic stresses [9; 10; 11]. It's one of the most important agents in various crops [12; 13]. Alginate is the most commonly used biopolymer for microorganisms [14]. A water-soluble polymer (chitosan) (pH<6) has been used in several studies for the microencapsulation of bacteria [15]. Costales et al. [16] investigated the viability of *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* inoculated with a chitosan polymer on seeds and the effects on seed improvement, bacterial viability, and nodulation in soybean upon inoculation polymer application at different storage times. The polymer had no effect on seed survival or bacterial viability. Jarecki, [17] showed in his study the effectiveness of commercial inoculation and improved coating (chitosan+alginate/ PEG) in a single or combined application on soybean seeds. According to the research, it's not very effective to apply only the coated seeds and it doesn't develop the appropriate number of nodules on the roots of soybean. Zeng and Zhang [18] developed a new coating for soybean seeds with carboxymethyl chitosan as the main component in the study. Compared to the control group, it was found that soybean seeds coated with the new seed coating material increased production yield by 18% while costing 26% less.

The effect of different chitosan concentrations on soybean growth and pest control was studied experimentally [19]. The results showed that the total chitosan coating had a significant effect on pest control when the concentration was increased. Rocha et al. [20], reported that the effects of using coated seeds depend on many factors, including plant species and habitat conditions. Zhou et al. [21] studied two rhizobium strains (ACCC17631 and ACCC17676) effective in the alfalfa cultivar Zhongmu No.1 with two different coating agents and different concentrations of ammonium molybdate in the seed coating. The 0.2% formulation of the ammonium molybdate treatment had the greatest effects on plant nitrogen fixation ability, nodulation, and development when inoculated with rhizobium strain ACCC17631. Since the rhizobium population in the soil is naturally insufficient, large-scale application of the above microbial fertilizers can significantly reduce the need for nitrogenous fertilizers and their negative impact on the environment. Rhizobium bacteria can be coated with natural, cheap, and widely available materials, which can lead to an increase in their availability.

The aim of this study, the viability of bacteria in seeds within 3 months was investigated by applying biomaterials such as chitosan and sodium alginate to bean seeds after inoculation of rhizobium bacteria, based on their ability to maintain and support living cells.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Test Plant

Plant material of the bean variety Yunus 90 from the Anadolu Agricultural Research Institute in Eskisehir, Turkey, was used for the study.

Bacterial Culture

The rhizobium strain (*Rhizobium phaseoli*) used in the study was obtained from the biological laboratories of the Central Research Institute of Soil, Fertilizer and Water Resources in Ankara. The rhizobium strain was grown in a yeast mannitol agar (YMA) medium. Inoculation was performed with the liquid formulation after increasing the bacterial concentration to 1×10^8 CFU/ml [22].

Biomaterials

A sodium alginate solution was prepared by mixing in pure water at 1% (w/w) in a mechanical mixer. Chitosan solution was prepared by mixing 1 ml of 1% (w/w) acetic acid solution in pure water in a mechanical mixer [23; 24; 25].

Growing Medium

Pots weighing 2 kg were filled with a sterilized sand and perlite mixture in a 1:1 ratio.

Nutrient Solution

After preparing the nutrient solution, 1 ml of each microelement solution was added per liter. The pots were watered with 1/5 diluted nutrient solution. Nutrient solution modified according to Arnon and Hogland was used in the experiment [26].

The experiment establishment

The study was conducted in computerized greenhouses in a randomized plot design with 3 replicates. In the study, bean seeds were inoculated with the bacterial strain prepared in a liquid formulation after seed surface sterilization with a 0.5% sodium chloride solution (sodium hypochlorite). Rhizobium bacteria isolated in seeds were coated with chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers prepared at concentrations of 1% held in solutions of chitosan and sodium alginate for 5 minutes. Seeds were coated and inoculated, then dried for 1-2 hours in a dark room, sealed, and stored for 3 months. At the end of 90 days, the greenhouse experiment was conducted under controlled conditions by planting the seeds in pots with sterile sand and perlite. In addition, seeds inoculated with bacteria and coated with biopolymers were planted simultaneously as controls. When flowering reached 50% or more, plants were harvested and the following parameters were measured (upper part and root length, wet and dry weight of upper, wet and dry weight of roots, number and weight of nodules, nitrogen in the upper part and roots) (AACC 2004).

Statistical Analysis

The differences in the variables attributed to treatments were analyzed with ANOVA using SPSS 10.0 software for Windows (SPSS Inc., USA). Duncan's multiple range test was used to determine significant differences in response to parameters. Statistical significance is indicated at 1% and 5% probability level.

RESULTS

Plant upper part height and root length

After coating some biopolymers (chitosan and sodium alginate) on bean seeds isolated with rhizobium bacteria and keeping them for three months, there were differences between the applications "inoculated, inoculated+chitosan and inoculated+sodium alginate" and the storage times in terms of the height of the upper part of the plants obtained from the planted seeds, although these differences weren't statistically significant.

Fig. 1. The effect of chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers coated on the surface of seeds inoculated with rhizobium bacteria and storage times on the upper part height and root length of the bean plant (I: Inoculation; I+C: Inoculation+Chitosan; I+SA: Inoculation+Sodium Alginate)

The highest height of the upper part of the plant 26.11 cm was obtained when the seed inoculated with bacteria was planted without delay. The lowest plant height of the upper part of the Yunus 90 bean cultivar was determined at a length of 24.22 cm when the seed inoculated with bacteria was planted after 90 days of storage. After bacterial inoculation, the lengths of the upper parts of the plants grown from chitosan-coated seeds that hadn't been maintained had lower values than the seeds that had been stored for three months. It was found that the differences between the applications "inoculated, inoculated + chitosan, and inoculated + sodium alginate" and the storage times (0.90 days) on the root length of the bean plant were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). It was found that the root lengths of Yunus 90 bean plants varied between 26.56-30.44 cm. The highest root length of 30.44 cm was observed in seeds (inoculated + sodium alginate) grown without a waiting period after the surface of the seed inoculated with bacteria was coated with sodium alginate biopolymer. It was also found that the highest value for root length was 29.44 cm after the seeds inoculated with chitosan biopolymer were grown and stored for 90 days. In contrast, the lowest root length of 26.56 cm was obtained when the inoculated seeds were planted without waiting.

Plant upper part wet weight and dry weight

Differences between treatments and storage times of chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers applied to bacteria-inoculated seeds weren't statistically significant, but differences between storage times were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The wet weight of the upper part of the plant was found to vary between 22.50-34.56 g. The highest wet weight of the upper part of the plant 34.56 g was determined by planting the seed inoculated with bacteria on the same day without coating with biopolymer. It was found that the wet weight values for the upper part were as follows: 28.57 g (inoculation+sodium alginate 0th day), 28.15 g (inoculation+sodium alginate 90th day), 28.08 g (inoculation+chitosan 90th day), 24.46 g (inoculation+chitosan 0th day) and 22.50 g (inoculation 90th day).

Fig. 2. The effect of chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers coated on the surface of seeds inoculated with rhizobium bacteria and storage times on the plant's upper part wet weight and upper part dry weight (g/plant) (I: Inoculation; I+C: Inoculation+Chitosan; I+SA: Inoculation+Sodium Alginate)

When seeds inoculated with bacteria were planted after 90 days of waiting without coating them with biopolymers, a 35% reduction in upper plant wet weight was observed compared to seeds planted without waiting. However, a 19% decrease in the upper wet weight was observed in plants coated with chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers 90 days after bacterial inoculation. The study found that the differences in the upper dry weight of Yunus 90 bean plant between applications of chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers applied to bean plant seeds inoculated with rhizobium bacteria weren't statistically significant. On the other hand, the differences between the dry weights of the upper parts of the bean plant after the seeds were coated with some biopolymers and kept for 3 months were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). It was found that the dry weight of the bean plant in the upper part varied from 3.57-6.07 g. The highest dry weight in the upper part of the plant of 6.07 g cm was determined in seeds planted without coating with biomaterials of bacteria-inoculated seeds and without a waiting period. The lowest dry weight of the upper part of the plant was 3.57 g and was observed in seeds inoculated with rhizobium bacteria without covering them with biological materials, grown and stored for 90 days. In the research, the dry weight values for the upper part were found to be as follows: 4.78 g (inoculation+sodium alginate 90th day), 4.63 g (inoculation+chitosan 90th day), 4.57 g (inoculation+sodium alginate 0th day), 4.00 g (inoculation+chitosan 0th day), and 3.57 g (inoculation 90th day). When seeds inoculated with bacteria were sown after 90 days of waiting without coating them with biopolymers, a 41% reduction in upper plant dry weight was observed compared to seeds sown without waiting. However, in the upper part of the dry weight of plants obtained after planting seeds coated with chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers and after bacterial inoculation followed by a 90-day waiting period, a decrease of 24% was observed for chitosan biopolymers and 21% for sodium alginate biopolymers.

Plant root wet weight and dry weight

Based on the results of the analysis of variance of the wet root weight of the bean plant, it was found that the differences between the applications (inoculation, inoculation+chitosan, inoculation+sodium alginate) were statistically insignificant. On the other hand, it was found that the effect of storage time on the wet weight of roots of seeds inoculated with bacteria after coating with some biomaterials was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). It was found that the root

wet weight of the bean plant changed from 28.89 to 33.44 g. The lowest root wet weight in seeds planted without a waiting period after inoculated seeds were covered with chitosan biopolymer (inoculation + chitosan) was 28.89 g.

Fig. 3. The effect of chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers coated on the surface of seeds inoculated with rhizobium bacteria and storage period on the plant root wet and dry weight (g/plant) (I: Inoculation; I+C: Inoculation+Chitosan; I+SA: Inoculation+Sodium Alginate)

The highest root wet weight was found to be 33.44 g when applied (inoculation+sodium alginate+0th day). The effects of chitosan biopolymers and sodium alginate-coated seeds inoculated with rhizobium bacteria and storage periods on the dry weight of bean plant roots were found to be non-significant between applications but were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) between storage periods. It was found that the dry weight of bean plant roots ranged from 1.99-2.97 g. The highest root dry weight of 2.97 g was determined for seeds inoculated and planted on the same day (0 days) and not covered with biomaterials. The lowest root dry weight was found to be 1.99 g in seeds inoculated with bacteria and stored for 90 days. It was found that covering the seeds with biopolymers after bacterial inoculation and waiting reduced the root dry weight of the plant.

Number of nodules and nodule weight

It was found that the differences between the applications (inoculation, inoculation+chitosan, inoculation+sodium alginate) of the biopolymers chitosan and sodium alginate applied to the surface of seeds inoculated with rhizobium bacteria and the storage times (0 and 90 days) were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) in terms of the number of plant nodules. It was found that the number of nodules in the bean plant ranged from 24.00- 95.33. Among the applications, the highest number of nodules (95.33 pieces) was observed in bean plants whose seeds were inoculated with rhizobium bacteria, not coated with biopolymers, and planted on the same day. On the other hand, the lowest number of nodules (24.00 pieces) was observed in seeds inoculated with bacteria, planted after coating with chitosan biopolymers and stored for 90 days. Compared with the inoculated control application, coating the bacteria-inoculated seeds with chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers negatively affected the viability of bacteria and resulted in a decrease in the number of nodules. It was suggested that chitosan and sodium alginate may have initially decreased bacterial viability due to their antibacterial properties. It was found that the number of nodules in the roots of plants planted from non-inoculated seeds or seeds coated with biopolymers decreased by 59% after a waiting period of 90 days. On the other hand, it was found that the number of nodules decreased by 49% in inoculated seeds coated with sodium alginate biopolymer and planted without a waiting period compared to the inoculated control group. However, it was found that the number of

nodules in the roots of plants planted with the same seed after 90 days of the waiting period decreased by 14%.

Fig. 4. The effect of chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers coated on the surface of seeds inoculated with rhizobium bacteria and storage period on the number of nodules (number/plant) and nodule weight (g/plant) (I: Inoculation; I+C: Inoculation+Chitosan; I+SA: Inoculation+Sodium Alginate)

As a result, it was found that by coating the seeds with biomaterials, especially the sodium alginate biopolymer, and storing the seeds within 3 months, the viability of rhizobium bacteria was maintained. The results of the analysis of variance of nodule weights taken from the root of the bean plant showed that there were differences between the applications (inoculated, inoculated+chitosan, inoculated+sodium alginate) and waiting periods (0 and 90 days) in terms of the nodules, and these differences were found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Compared to the inoculated control application, coating the bean seeds inoculated with rhizobium bacteria with chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers negatively affected the viability of the bacteria and reduced the number of nodules in the roots of the plants, resulting in a reduction in nodule weight. It was found that the weights of nodules in the bean plant ranged from 0.27-0.69 grams. The highest nodule weight of 0.69 g was found when seeds were inoculated with bacteria applied and planted without a waiting period. On the other hand, the lowest nodule weight at the root of the bean plant, 0.27 g, was found in seeds planted after inoculation with rhizobium bacteria and coating with chitosan biopolymers and kept for 90 days. It was also found that the chitosan biopolymer caused a 46% reduction and the sodium alginate biopolymer caused a 38% reduction in nodule weight when seeds were planted without a waiting period compared to the inoculated control application. However, while nodule weights in the roots of plants for the inoculated application were reduced by 48% from seeds that were inoculated, coated, and stored for 3 months, the chitosan biopolymer decreased by 27% and the sodium alginate biopolymer decreased by 5%.

Plant upper part and root N content

According to the results of variance analysis of the nitrogen contents of the upper parts of the bean plant that were collected from the root of the bean plant, it was determined that there were differences between the applications (inoculated, inoculated+chitosan, inoculated+sodium alginate) and waiting periods (0 and 90 days) on the nitrogen contents of the upper parts of the bean plant, and these differences were found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). On the other hand, the effects of storage periods on the nitrogen content in the upper part of the plant varied, but this difference was not statistically significant. It has been found that the nitrogen content of the bean plant varies between 2.50-2.91%.

Fig. 5. The effect of chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers coated on the surface of seeds inoculated with rhizobium bacteria and storage period on the nitrogen content of the upper parts and root of the bean plant (%) (I: Inoculation; I+C: Inoculation+Chitosan; I+SA: Inoculation+Sodium Alginate)

The highest nitrogen content was determined by planting the seeds (90. days inoculated+ sodium alginate) after coating the bacteria-inoculated seeds with sodium alginate with 2.91% and storing them for 90 days. This was achieved by sowing seeds inoculated with rhizobium bacteria with a nitrogen content of 2.78% in the bean plant, which was stored for 90 days after coating with sodium alginate. The lowest nitrogen content in the plant, 2.50%, was obtained by planting seeds inoculated with bacteria without a waiting period. On the other hand, based on the research data, it was found that coating the bacteria-inoculated seeds with the biopolymer chitosan and the storage period had a lower effect on the nitrogen content of the plant in the upper part than the other biopolymer. It was found that the nitrogen levels in the upper part of the plant were higher in the seeds planted 90 days after inoculation and coated with biomaterial. Biopolymers of chitosan and sodium alginate coated on seeds inoculated with rhizobium bacteria showed differences in nitrogen content in bean plant roots between applications and storage times, and these differences were found to be statistically insignificant. It was found that nitrogen contents in Yunus 90 bean plant roots ranged from 1.42-1.60%. The nitrogen content in plant root (1.60%) was obtained by sowing seeds inoculated with rhizobium bacteria without a waiting period. The nitrogen content (1.60%) in plant roots was obtained by planting the seeds inoculated with rhizobium bacteria without a waiting period. In addition, this value was determined for seeds planted without a waiting period and the inoculated seeds were coated with sodium alginate polymer. The lowest nitrogen content in the root of the bean plant was found to be 1.42% in seeds planted 90 days after bacterial inoculation and coated with sodium alginate biopolymer.

DISCUSSION

Our results showed differences in the effects of coating with chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers on some yield components and nodulation data after seed inoculation with rhizobium. However, coating with sodium alginate biopolymer proved to be more effective than chitosan biopolymer in improving some yield components and protecting bacterial viability. Sodium alginate is the sodium salt of alginic acid. The main source of alginic acid is brown algae. Alginate is found in the cell walls of algae, similar to cellulose in plants, and acts like cellulose to maintain the structural shape of the cell. It also acts as alginic acid by binding

water and supplying water to the algae in the absence of water so that they don't dry out. Advantages of coating with alginate: slow and controlled release of bacteria, biodegradation of soil, and extended shelf life [28; 29; 6]. In addition, it may reduce some bacteria over time, but the remaining bacterial population is sufficient [30]. However, its use in agriculture is limited due to sensitivities when applied during the conventional inoculation process. To increase the use of microbial fertilizer, seeds can be inoculated with microorganisms and coated with biomaterials instead of using them as usual. This can extend the use of microbial fertilizer and partially extend the shelf life of the bacteria. Coating inoculated bacteria on the surface of seeds can increase cell viability during storage and inoculated bacterial cells can be released into the target medium in a slow and controlled manner with long-term improvement effectiveness. Also, after a long storage period, the bacteria have not lost their ability to promote plant growth [4]. The main criteria for the selection of carriers of nodule-forming bacteria are cheapness, ease of use, moisture capacity, and non-toxicity [31]. Although there are different formulations of commercial rhizobium inoculants, their use is limited due to the low viability of bacteria in seeds stored in inappropriate environmental conditions [32; 40]. These effects include macromolecule dehydration as a result of toxic oxygen levels and high temperatures [33]. Therefore, storing plants at lower temperatures and adding replacement inoculants (polymeric adhesives) are used to improve the rhizobial microenvironment to reduce the impact on seed yield and nodulation and increase the seedling survival ratios [34]. The hydrophobic polymer applied to soybean seeds was especially effective in regulating water absorption after planting when soil moisture was unfavorable and improving plant germination and emergence [35]. Tripathi et al. [36]; found that coating soybean seeds with a polymer based on natural substances effectively improved the germination rate. Jeyabal et al. [37]; found that coating soybean seeds with organic or inorganic substances increased the number of pods per plant. Although chitosan has a wide spectrum of antimicrobial activity, it exhibits different inhibition efficiencies against different fungi and gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria [38]. Previous studies on seed treatments with chitosan reported a significant or no effect on seed quality [7], whereas other forms of chitosan treatments were more effective in maintaining seed viability and viability for several months [12]. Shcherbakova et al. [6]; in their study, they found that inoculation of chickpea and soybean seeds with *Mesorhizobium ciceri* ST-282 and *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* M8 and coating with alginate pellets significantly increased the number and weight of nodules. Jarecki [17]; conducted his study to demonstrate the effectiveness of developed coating (chitosan+alginate/PEG) and commercial inoculant in alone or combination applications to soybean seeds. In the research, it has been shown that it is not very effective in planting only coated seeds and that the appropriate number of nodules does not develop on soybean roots. Bacterial isolates in the alginate-based formulation retained root colonization, antifungal, and enzyme activity during storage [39]. According to Rocha et al. [20]; the effects of using coated seeds depend on a lot of factors, such as plant species or habitat conditions.

CONCLUSION

According to data obtained after the inoculation of dry bean seeds, it was determined that the use of chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers significantly decreased the viability of bacteria as compared to the inoculating control application. In the chitosan application, bacterial viability decreased with an increasing storage period, but there was a slight increase in the sodium alginate application depending on the storage time. Our results showed that the coating of biopolymers of chitosan and sodium alginate on inoculated legume seeds generally showed differences in some yield components and the nodulation values of bean plants

according to the biopolymers, and it was determined that it caused an increase and decrease in yield components. As a result, dry bean seeds coated with a biodegradable biopolymer (chitosan/sodium alginate) and stored for a long time (90 days) after bacterial inoculation on the surface of the seed partially increased nodulation in the root zone and some yield components. On the other hand, after coating with biomaterials, it was observed that the biopolymer, especially sodium alginate, protected the rhizobium bacterial population by about 50% within 3 months of the seed storage period.

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